

TABLE 3 - THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF BINARY COMPLEXES

$\mu = 0.1 M$, Temp. = 35°

Metal ion	Ligand	ΔG_1	ΔG_2 kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG°	ΔH_1	ΔH_2 kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH°	ΔS_1	ΔS_2 JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔS°
La	2-TPA			21.99			4.03			58.31
	3-TPA			22.35			7.24			49.01
	3-(2-TE)AA			24.47			11.99			40.52
	2-TPA	19.81	17.16	36.96 (36.97)	5.08	2.22	7.30 (7.62)	47.82	48.50	96.32 (95.29)
	3-TPA	19.22	16.63	34.85 (34.85)	8.42	4.37	12.79 (15.25)	31.79	39.28	71.57 (63.63)
	3-(2-TE)AA	18.45	16.39	34.84 (34.85)	15.25	7.62	22.87 (24.64)	10.40	28.47	38.47 (33.16)
Gd	2-TPA	18.16	16.45	34.61 (34.61)	2.78	1.38	4.17 (4.38)	49.93	48.90	98.83 (98.00)
	3-TPA	17.45	16.74	34.19 (34.20)	4.37	3.65	7.62 (7.46)	41.79	44.45	86.24 (86.81)
	3-(2-TE)AA	12.69	16.27	33.96 (34.00)	3.98	1.90	5.88 (5.49)	44.50	46.65	91.15 (90.84)
Dy	2-TPA	18.16	16.57	34.73 (34.73)	2.17	2.23	4.40 (4.32)	51.89	46.54	98.43 (98.75)
	3-TPA	17.57	16.27	33.84 (33.85)	13.92	5.63	9.55 (17.16)	11.85	34.57	46.42 (54.18)
	3-(2-TE)AA	21.99	16.63	38.62 (38.62)	9.15	8.58	17.73 (12.54)	41.70	26.13	67.83 (68.44)

*Values in parenthesis have been calculated from the mean values as given in the parenthesis in Tables 1 and 2.

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Volumetric and Transport Properties of Chromium Sulphate in Aqueous Mixtures of Urea and Thiourea

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THE study of ion solvation in mixed solvents has attracted the attention of large number of workers only during the last few years. It has been realised that ion solvation can be better understood in mixed solvents than in pure solvents, because the dielectric constant and viscosity of the medium can be varied to a desired value in the mixed solvents. For the study of ion-solvent interactions, water has been used extensively as

a component in mixed solvents due to its easy availability and high dielectric constant. There are various types of interactions which exist between ions in solutions, of these, solute-solvent interactions appear to be most important. The volumetric and viscosity behaviour of solutes in solution can provide information concerning solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions¹. The infinite dilution partial molar volumes are by definition, independent of solute-solute interactions, and can be used to examine solute-solvent interactions. The survey of literature shows that very little work has been done in aqueous-nonelectrolyte mixtures. The present work has therefore been carried out to learn more about solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions of chromium sulphate in aqueous mixtures of urea and thiourea.

Experimental

Chromium sulphate, urea and thiourea (all AnalaR) were used as such after drying over sulphuric acid. Freshly distilled conductivity water (sp. cond. 10⁻⁶ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹) was used for preparing the urea-water and thiourea-water mixtures as well as standard liquid. The urea-water, thiourea-water mixtures of varying compositions as well as the solutions of chromium sulphate were made by weight and molalities were converted into molarities using the standard expression².

Densities were measured with an apparatus similar to the one reported by Ward and Millero³ and described elsewhere⁴. The apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) were calculated from the density data

using the expression,

$$\phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d_o} + \frac{1000(d_o - d)}{Cd_o} \quad (1)$$

where C is the molarity of the electrolyte, d the density of the electrolytic solution, d_o the density of solvent (water+urea or thiourea) and M_2 the molecular weight of chromium sulphate.

The kinematic viscosities were measured with the help of a Ostwald's suspended level type viscometer with a flow time of 498 s for water (301 K). Runs were repeated until three successive determinations were obtained within ± 0.1 s. The relative viscosities (η_r) of the solutions were calculated using the relation,

$$\eta_r = \eta/\eta_o = dt/d_o t_o \quad (2)$$

where the symbols have usual significance.

The density and viscosity measurements were carried out in a water-bath whose temperature was kept constant ($\pm 0.01^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) was calculated from the density data using equation (1). It was found to vary linearly with the square-root of concentration in conformity with the Masson's equation⁵,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^o + S_v^* \sqrt{C} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ_v^o is the limiting apparent molar volume and is equal to partial molar volume V_2^o at infinite dilution and S_v^* the experimental slope. A sample plot for chromium sulphate in different compositions of urea-water at 303 K is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Plots of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} for chromium sulphate in different compositions of urea-water at 303 K: (○) 11.52%, (□) 20.31%, (△) 29.64% and (▽) 36.83% urea-water.

The partial molar volume at infinite dilution (ϕ_v^o) and the experimental slope (S_v^*) data for chromium sulphate in different composition of urea-water (11.52, 20.31, 29.64 and 36.83% urea, w/w) and thiourea-water (3, 6, 9 and 12% thiourea, w/w) at 303 K were derived using the method of least-squares (Table 1). It is evident from Table 1 that S_v^* is negative in the entire composition of urea as well as thiourea at 303 K. Since S_v^* is a measure of ion-ion interactions, the results indicate that ion-ion interactions are weak for chromium sulphate in urea-water and thiourea-water mixtures at 303 K.

TABLE 1 - VALUES OF ϕ_v^o , S_v^* AND STANDARD ERROR FOR CHROMIUM SULPHATE IN DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS OF UREA-WATER AND THIOUREA-WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE*

Solvent composition	Temp. K	ϕ_v^o cm ³ mol ⁻¹	S_v^* cm ³ lit ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2}
Urea-Water			
11.52	303	347.68 (5.05)*	-1274.44 (52.68)
20.31	303	420.91 (3.31)	-1260.07 (36.96)
29.64	303	371.70 (4.35)	-1249.39 (44.32)
36.83	303	462.82 (4.20)	-1501.79 (42.35)
Thiourea-Water			
3.00	303	252.16 (4.19)	-77.01 (7.31)
6.00	303	242.54 (4.22)	-52.29 (7.55)
9.00	303	240.61 (3.96)	-52.74 (7.05)
12.00	303	259.19 (5.09)	-88.82 (11.56)
Urea-Water			
11.52	298	370.56 (2.35)	-1279.35 (24.53)
	303	347.65 (5.05)	-1274.44 (52.68)
	308	311.74 (1.04)	1268.48 (10.85)
	313	293.44 (1.79)	-1267.01 (12.75)
Thiourea-Water			
3.00	303	252.16 (4.19)	-77.01 (7.31)
	308	236.96 (5.55)	-62.58 (9.70)
	313	230.87 (1.57)	-53.91 (2.75)
	318	223.06 (2.52)	-41.64 (4.41)

*Standard errors given in parentheses.

Further, since ϕ_v^0 is a measure of ion-solvent interactions, it is evident from Table 1 that the values of ϕ_v^0 are positive in urea-water as well as thiourea-water mixtures indicating thereby the presence of strong ion-solvent interactions. Since the behaviour of chromium sulphate was found to be identical in different compositions of urea-water as well as thiourea-water at 303 K, only 11.52% urea-water and 3% thiourea-water compositions were selected to study the effect of temperature.

The linear plots of ϕ_v vs $C^{\frac{1}{2}}$ have been obtained at different temperatures for chromium sulphate in both the systems. The values of ϕ_v^0 and S_v^* at different temperatures are also recorded in Table 1. It is evident that the value of S_v^* is negative in both the systems in the entire range of temperature studied, which indicates that ion-ion interactions though weak in the entire range of temperature but increase with the increase of temperature.

The temperature dependence of ϕ_v^0 for chromium sulphate in 11.52% urea-water and 3% thiourea-water can be expressed by the following equations :

$$\phi_v^0 = 6641 - 35.98T + 0.050T^2 \quad (4)$$

in 11.52% urea-water system (a 99% confidence interval for slope is -4.59 ± 0.65),

$$\phi_v^0 = 9971 - 60.85T + 0.095T^2 \quad (5)$$

in 3% thiourea-water system (a 99% confidence interval for slope is -2.34 ± 1.47).

The apparent molar expansibilities $\phi_E^0 = [\partial \phi_v^0 / \partial T]_p$ calculated from equations (4) and (5) indicate that ϕ_E^0 increases with increase of temperature. The increase in magnitude per degree temperature is positive indicating thereby that the behaviour of chromium sulphate is just like the behaviour of symmetrical tetraalkylammonium salts⁶, but not

Fig. 2. Variation of ϕ_E^0 with temperature for chromium sulphate in 11.52% urea-water.

like common electrolytes⁷. The variation of ϕ_E^0 with temperature is linear for chromium sulphate in

both the systems (a sample plot is shown in Fig 2 for urea-water). This positive increase of temperature can be ascribed to 'caging effect'⁸.

Hepler⁸ has developed a technique of examining the sign of $[\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_p$ for various solutes in terms of long-range structure making and breaking capacity of the solute using the general thermodynamic equation,

$$[\partial \bar{C}_p / \partial p]_T = -[\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_p \quad (6)$$

On the basis of this equation, it has been deduced that structure-making solute should have positive value, whereas structure-breaking solute negative value. In the present case $[\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_p$ is positive in both the systems, indicating thereby that chromium sulphate behaves as structure-maker/promotor.

Fig. 3. Plots of $\eta/\eta_0 - 1$ vs \sqrt{C} for chromium sulphate in different compositions of urea-water at 303 K. (O) 11.52%, (□) 20.31%, (▲) 29.64% and (Δ) 36.83% urea-water.

The relative viscosities of chromium sulphate in urea-water (11.52, 20.31, 29.64 and 36.83% urea, w/w) and thiourea-water (3, 6, 9 and 12% thiourea, w/w) were determined at 303 K. Since the viscosity behaviour of chromium sulphate was found to be identical in different compositions of urea-water and thiourea-water, the relative viscosity for chromium sulphate was determined only in 11.52 and 3%, urea-water and thiourea-water respectively, at different temperatures to know the effect of temperature. The data for relative viscosities were fitted to Jones-Dole⁹ equation (a sample plot is shown in Fig. 3),

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + AC^{\frac{1}{2}} + BC \quad (7)$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and solvent (urea-water or thiourea-water) respectively, C is the molar concentration of chromium

sulphate and A and B are constants which are specific for a given solute-solvent system. The A and B coefficients for chromium sulphate in both the mixtures studied here were also derived using the method of least-squares and are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF A AND B COEFFICIENTS AND STANDARD ERROR FOR CHROMIUM SULPHATE IN UREA-WATER AND THIOUREA-WATER MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES*

Solvent composition wt %	Temp. K	A dm ³ /s mol ⁻¹ /s	B dm ³ mol ⁻¹
Urea-Water			
11.52	303	0.088 (0.001)*	0.300 (0.011)
20.31	303	0.116 (0.001)	0.320 (0.002)
29.64	303	0.208 (0.001)	0.372 (0.017)
36.83	303	0.049 (0.002)	0.362 (0.020)
Thiourea-Water			
3.00	303	-0.357 (0.035)	2.419 (0.062)
6.00	303	-0.200 (0.025)	2.000 (0.044)
9.00	303	-0.304 (0.039)	2.152 (0.069)
12.00	303	-0.442 (0.013)	2.164 (0.297)
Urea-Water			
11.52	298	0.043 (0.001)	0.294 (0.012)
	303	0.088 (0.001)	0.288 (0.011)
	308	0.110 (0.002)	0.277 (0.017)
	313	0.071 (0.002)	0.252 (0.019)
Thiourea-Water			
3.00	303	-0.357 (0.035)	2.419 (0.062)
	308	-0.370 (0.013)	2.363 (0.055)
	313	-0.305 (0.022)	2.296 (0.039)
	318	-0.288 (0.030)	2.187 (0.052)

*Standard errors are given in parentheses.

It is evident from Table 2 that the values of A parameter, for chromium sulphate in different solutions of urea-water are positive and small, indicating thereby the presence of weak ion-ion interactions. But the viscosity A coefficients, for chromium sulphate, in various solutions of thiourea-water at 303 K and in 3% thiourea-water at different temperatures have negative values. Although this has

no physical significance¹⁰, similar observations have already been reported for tetraalkylammonium salts and for some 1 : 1 electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents¹¹. Similar difficulty was also encountered by Kay *et al.*¹² in some tetraalkylammonium salts in aqueous solutions. This error may be attributed to a surface tension effect resulting from minute traces of surface active impurities in thiourea and chromium sulphate.

Further, the B -coefficients for chromium sulphate are positive and large in the entire composition range of urea-water as well as thiourea-water at 303 K suggesting thereby the existence of strong ion-solvent interactions.

Further, linear plots have also been obtained for chromium sulphate in both the mixtures of urea-water and thiourea-water at different temperatures in conformity with Jones-Dole equation. The A and B parameters obtained using the method of least-squares are also listed in Table 2. The magnitude of B is positive in the entire range of temperature and decreases with increase in temperature indicating thereby that ion-solvent interactions decrease with increase in temperature. Further, the negative temperature coefficient (dB/dT) of B in case of 11.52% urea-water and 3% thiourea-water suggests¹³ that chromium sulphate behaves as structure-maker/promotor in both the mixtures. This conclusion is in excellent agreement with that drawn from partial molar volume data.

Viscosity data have also been analysed on the basis of a transition treatment as suggested by Feakins *et al.*¹⁴. The B -parameter in terms of this theory is given by equation (8),

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000v} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0}{1000} \left[\frac{\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}}{RT} \right] \quad (8)$$

where \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 are the partial molar volumes of solvent and solute (at infinite dilution) respectively, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is the contribution per mole of solute to the free energy of activation for viscous flow of the solution and $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ the free energy of activation per mole of the pure solvent and is given by¹⁵ equation (9),

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#} = \Delta G_1^\ddagger = RT \ln (\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0 / hN) \quad (9)$$

where h is the Planck constant, N the Avogadro number and η the viscosity of the solvent.

Now equation (8) can also be written as

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\#} + \frac{RT}{\bar{V}_1^0} [1000B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (10)$$

To estimate $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, it is necessary to know $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$. This parameter was calculated from relation (9). The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ are recorded in Table 3. The partial molar volume \bar{V}_1^0 of urea and thiourea at infinite dilution was found to be 42.22 and 45.20 cm³ mol⁻¹ respectively at 303 K. The values obtained from equation (10) for chromium sulphate in different compositions of urea-water and thiourea-water at 303 K are given in Table 3. It is evident that $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ values are practically constant at all

TABLE 3 - VALUES OF $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ AND $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ IN UREA-WATER AND THIOUREA-WATER AT 303 K

Solvent % (w/w)	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹
Chromium sulphate in urea-water		
11.52	11.39	46.75
20.31	11.62	54.03
29.64	11.90	53.58
36.83	12.16	59.52
Chromium sulphate in thiourea-water		
3.0	11.38	26.18
6.0	11.42	24.38
9.0	11.46	24.78
12.0	11.48	28.43

solvent compositions in each system. This implies that $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ may be determined by B -coefficient and $(\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)$ term. The positive values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ in both the systems, suggest that flow rate is not favoured by urea or thiourea content. Moreover, the value of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ has been found to be greater than that of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ in both the systems at 303 K, again conforming our conclusions from molar volume and viscosity data that chromium sulphate acts as a structure-maker/promotor in the entire range of solvent composition of urea-water and thiourea-water.

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Auranamide—A Phenylalanine Derivative from *Grangea maderaspatana* Poir.

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IN pursuance of our interest in Indian Compositae, we have recently reinvestigated *G. maderaspatana* and reported several clerodane, *nor*-clerodane, *seco*-clerodane, *nor-seco*-clerodane derivatives alongwith phenylalanine, hardwickiic and strictic acid derivatives¹. The phenylalanine derivative has been identified as auranamide (1) by Banerji and Ray². Subsequently, Talapatra *et al.*³ obtained the same compound and designated it as anabellamide. Previous work on this plant led to the isolation of a number of clerodane derivatives, polyacetylenes, flavones^{4,5}, chondrillasterol and chondrillasterone⁶.

Experimental

The air dried aerial parts (2 kg) of *G. maderaspatana* (obtained from M/s United Chemicals and Allied Products, Calcutta) were extracted with Et₂O-petrol-MeOH (1 : 1 : 1) mixture for 24 h in cold and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure giving a greenish mass which was defatted by dissolving in MeOH and leaving overnight at 0°. The concentrated extract was column chromatographed over silica gel (B.D.H. ; 60 - 120 mesh) and following four fractions were collected: fraction-1 (petrol), fraction-2 (petrol-Et₂O, 3 : 1), fraction-3 (petrol-Et₂O, 1 : 1) and fraction-4 (Et₂O), Fraction-1 furnished α -humulene (40 mg). Fraction-2 was a complex mixture and separated on PTLC (SiO₂, PF 254) using C₆H₆-CH₂Cl₂ (1 : 1) solvent mixture affording phytol (200 mg), 3-hydroxy-8-acetoxy-pentadeca-1,9,14-trien-4,6-diene (10 mg), lupeol (40 mg) and a mixture of diterpene acids (400 mg) which on subsequent methylation with ethereal CH₂N₂ and hplc separation (MeOH-H₂O, 9 : 1) over RP 18 (analytical column) gave methyl-10-*epi*-nidoresedoate (30 mg; R_t 11.8 min), methyl strictiate (100 mg; R_t 12.7 min), a mixture of methyl esters of centipedic and nidoresedic acids (170 mg; R_t 15.0 min) and methyl hardwickiate